

TENSILE TESTING CHARACTERIZATION OF ASYMMETRICALLY TAPERED COMPOSITE LAMINATES

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1. Abstract

Tapering composite laminates requires terminating plies, i.e. dropping-off fibre reinforced layers. Ply terminations generate through-the-thickness stress discontinuities and this promotes delamination. Extensive research has been focused on the onset and growth of delaminations from ply drop-off. This paper addresses the experimental characterization of quasi-isotropic asymmetrically tapered laminates loaded in axial tension. A high-speed camera has been used to capture the location of ply de-bond initiation and the subsequent delamination propagation. The experimentally assessed strength has been compared to the failure loads predicted employing an existing analytical method and finite element analysis based on the virtual crack closure technique.

2. Introduction

The behaviour of tapered composite laminates under static and fatigue loading has been widely addressed in the literature [1-7]. Petrossian and Wisnom [8] have demonstrated that interlaminar shear stresses are responsible for transferring loads from the dropped-off plies to the continuous sub-laminates and this tends to promote delamination. Therefore the ply relative stiffness has a great influence on both the tensile and bending strengths of tapered laminates. The laminate ultimate strength can be predicted by considering the energy release rate ERR associated with the delaminations emanated from ply drop-offs [9]. This approach was first validated for cut-ply specimens, where there is no tapering angle and it is valid only for mode II thick section delaminations. However, recent work [10] has suggested that the laminate tapering angle governs the onset load and the location of delaminations emanated from ply drop-offs. Wisnom et al. showed [12] that an “aggressive” tapering angle, i.e. equal to or larger than 20°,

promotes the initiation of the delamination at the thin laminate section. This is mainly due to the straightening of the outer plies at the ply drop-off location. Once the thin section delamination has initiated, it typically grows to a length ranging from 5 to 10 times the thickness of the terminated blocks. Then delaminations occur in the thick section and these are responsible for the specimen final failure.

In this paper a “bulged” specimen configuration is considered, as shown in fig. 1. This is representative of integral composite skin stiffeners widely employed in aeronautical structures. Despite the vast literature addressing the effect of ply drop-offs on the strength of tapered laminates, a bulged configuration has not been characterised in tension before. The effect of ply terminations on the tensile strength of bulged tapered specimens is here examined via a comprehensive experimental characterization followed by finite element modelling. The onset of delamination in the specimens is here studied using the closed form ERR expression derived in Ref. [13]. The experimental and analytical results are then compared to FE simulations performed employing the virtual crack closure technique (VCCT) available in Abaqus Standard [15-16].

3. Experimental tests

3.1. Specimen manufacture

Three 250 mm x 280 mm panel were manufactured using IM7/8552 carbon fibre/epoxy prepreg. The following laminate stacking sequence was considered: [0 45 -45 0 0 -45 45 0]_N, where N denotes the number of blocks. As shown in fig.1, the specimens had N=4 at the central “bulge”, i.e. at the thick section, while N=3 at the thin section. Three different distances between the ply drop-offs were considered, respectively 5, 10 and 20mm, as shown again in fig. 1.

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Figure 1. Tensile specimens configuration, with $a = 5, 10$ and 20 mm

The nominal cured ply thickness was 0.127 mm , giving a final overall thickness of 4.15 mm for the thick section and 3.2 mm for the thin section.

Figure 2. Picture of the panels manufacturing ($5, 10$ and 20 mm inserted ply dropped width)

The panels were cut in 15 mm wide strips along the 0° plies direction. Glass fibre end tabs were bonded to each extremity of the specimens. The specimen gauge lengths ranged from 125 to 140 mm , depending on the various “inter-drop-off” distances. The plies were laid-up on a flat metal plate tooling. Due to the high vacuum pressure applied during the consolidation and the following cure, the dropped plies slightly sunk into the core sub-laminate, thus reducing the actual tapering angle as shown in fig. 3.

Figure 3. Angle formed by the ply drop-off

In fig. 3 ϕ is the average post-cure tapering angle

$$\phi = \tan^{-1} \frac{t^*}{L} \quad (1)$$

where t^* is the thickness of the terminated block and L is the length over which the transition from the thick section to the thin one takes place, i.e. the resin pocket length. The average post-cure tapering angle was 30° . The specimens considered here have

symmetric stacking sequences for both the thick and the thin section. This choice is motivated by the fact that significant bowing of asymmetrically tapered specimens was observed when asymmetric stacking sequences had been employed for tapered specimens [12]. It is worth recalling that the sub-laminate which is laid on top of the resin pocket is commonly denoted as “belt”, while the “core” sub-laminate is that running below the resin pocket.

3.2. Testing

The specimens were loaded using a displacement controlled rate of 1 mm/min in an Instron 100 kN load cell machine. One of the specimens was instrumented with strain gauges fixed on the thin section top and bottom surfaces at a distance of 30 mm from the ply termination.

Three specimens were tested in each batch of inter-drop-off distances. During the tests, videos were recorded using a high speed camera to capture the onset and propagation of the delaminations in the neighbourhood of a single ply drop-off.

3.3. Results

Representative experimental load vs cross-head displacement curves are shown fig. 4 for each of the three batches. No significant variations were observed among the batches in terms of load to failure. Therefore the tensile nominal strength was averaged over the whole set of samples, regardless of the inter-drop distance. The experimental failure load of the specimens was $46.2 \pm 2\text{ kN}$.

Figure 4. Load vs head-cross displacement of tensile specimens

The experimental load/cross-head displacement curves in fig. 4 show a progressive loss of stiffness, which is associated to the onset and growth of

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delaminations. The experimental load to initiate the crack was determined by considering a maximum deviation of 5% of the force versus strain curves from a linear trend. By virtue of this criterion, the delamination onset occurred at 23.8kN applied load. The strain gauge readings show now deviation from a linear trend at the onset load mentioned above and up until final failure. This implies that, if any delamination propagation took place at the thin section, the resulting interlaminar crack had to be significantly shorter than the distance between the ply termination and the strain gauge, i.e. 30 mm.

A high speed camera has been used to capture the delamination initiation. In order to work out the frame rate required for the camera, the speed of sound in the orthotropic material has to be considered. As demonstrated in [14], a frame rate of 360000/s allows obtaining a reasonably fluid video, although the observed area was limited to 128 x 48 pixels. All the 9 specimens failed progressively; this allowed observing the crack onset location via the high speed setup described above. Fig.5 shows the delamination paths observed during testing.

Figure 5. Delamination paths

The first delamination was observed at the thin section. Then, due to straightening of the belt sub-laminate, a short delamination was also observed at the top interface in the thick section, as shown in fig.6. Subsequently, the specimen catastrophic failure occurred due to a delamination growing along the lower interface in the thick section

Figure 6. Crack initiation picture of tensile specimens

Analytical model

The ultimate tensile strength to initiate a delamination was calculated using the analytical formula proposed by Petrossian and Wisnom [8]. The secondary bending moment Z , resulting from the neutral axis offset in the “bulged” thick section, had to be considered in the calculation. One has

$$Z = \frac{-Pt_{thick}}{2} \frac{\chi(1-d)(1-\chi)^3}{d+(1-d)(1-\chi)^3} \quad (2)$$

where P is the applied load, t_{thick} is the thick section thickness, d is the ratio of the thin section length and the specimen overall gauge length ($d=D/L$, as sketched in fig.5) and χ is ratio of the number of dropped plies with respect to the total number of layers comprised in the laminate.

The mode II toughness used to estimate the ultimate load to initiate a crack for the IM7/8552 material was assumed to be 1.18N/mm, [17]. This value takes into consideration the through-thickness compression of the laminate which occurs at the thick section due to the applied tensile loaded. The ERR formula in Ref. [8] predicts a delamination initiation load of 32.5 kN for the thick section, i.e. 2.2 kN/mm. However, this formula does not account for the presence of a thin section delamination, which is actually responsible for initiating the failure, as shown by the high speed videos.

5. Finite element modelling of progressive failure

3.4. Model

The modelling strategy adopted here was similar that outlined in Ref.[14]. The progressive failure analyses was carried out using the Abaqus Standard implicit Finite element (FE) solver. For the 20mm inter-drop distance, two FE models have been built based on the same mesh, one using plane stress elements and the other employing plane strain elements. Since the difference in terms of predicted strength was 0.3% between the two models, the 5 mm and 10 mm inter-drop distance cases were studied using the plane stress CPS3 and CPS4 fully integrated elements only. The laminate properties for IM7/8552 are listed in tab. 1 [14].

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The resin pocket was modelled assuming that the corresponding elastic properties were those of the neat 8552 epoxy matrix [19]. Half of the specimen was meshed and symmetry boundary conditions were imposed at the specimen mid-span plane. Multiple point constraints have been defined at the thin section end in order to simulate the uniform displacement due to the jig. A tensile force has been applied to one of the constrained nodes. The three candidate de-bond paths were the same considered in [14], along which the delamination actually occurred during the tests. The delamination growth was simulated using the VCCT implementation available in Abaqus. VCCT is based on computing the ERR using displacements and nodal forces at the crack tips. Krueger [15] carried out an assessment of the Abaqus VCCT capabilities for delamination simulation considering standard DCB samples and single lap joints. He concluded that the Abaqus VCCT implementation typically provides consistent results when compared to experimental data, although there are four analysis parameters related to viscous regularization which need to be tuned via time consuming sensitivity studies. In the model considered here the VCCT progressive failure simulation was run with the large displacement option activated, i.e. the analyses were geometrically non linear.

In principle the delamination propagation paths should extend along the edges of the resin pocket, but the toughness values for the interface between the neat resin and the composite laminate are not available, so VCCT could not be applied there. However the observation of the specimens under the microscope after curing had pointed out that a vertical crack was present at edge of the terminated ply block [14]. This crack is due to difference in thermal expansion between the bulk laminate and the neat resin pocket and occurs during the cooling down which follows the cure, prior the application of any mechanical loading. The crack often appears in an upside-down “V” shaped arrangement, so that the resin pocket inclined edge is also separated from the belt sub-laminate. The aforementioned crack was therefore introduced in the FE models, but surface contact pairs were defined at the dropped plies/resin pocket and at the belt/resin pocket interfaces in order avoid element co-penetration due to interlaminar compression.

E_1 (MPa)	E_3 (MPa)	G_{13} (MPa)	G_{12} (MPa)	G_{23} (MPa)	ν_{13}	ν_{12}	ν_{23}
90833	13437	4866	23373	4264	0.14	0.8	0.35

Table 1. Homogenized mechanical properties of IM7/8552

Figure 7. Delamination paths (dots) and contact surface locations (grey lines)

3.5. Results and discussion

The FE simulations run in Abaqus identified the same failure onset mechanism observed during testing. The first crack propagated at the thin section when the applied load reached 21.86kN for the 20mm inter-drop distance, 21.15kN for the 10mm case and finally 19.5kN for the 5mm distance. Subsequently, the 20mm inter-drop distance model showed that the top thick section path opens at 24.9kN, while the thin section delamination propagated to a length of 5mm and then stopped. The variation of the load to propagate the delamination for each inter-drop-off distance is at the most 10%, which is consistent with the experimental observation that the inter-drop distance itself plays a minor role in determining the ultimate strength.

Figure 8. Load vs Strain experimental and finite element comparison

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Therefore the FE results are here given in terms of the average load value to propagate the crack, which was found to be 20.8 kN.

Strain gauges have been used to monitor the strain at the thin section during loading. The strain values recorded during the testing were compared to the numerical predictions in order to assess if the model stiffness agreed with the experimental one. The crosshead displacement is not directly comparable to the node translation in the model due to the finite compliance of the loading fixture. Nonetheless fig. 6 shows that there is a good agreement between the experimental load/strain curves and those obtained from the simulations.

Finally an image-based high-fidelity FE model was developed to represent the uneven thickness of the belt sub-laminate and the associated progressive change of orientation of the reinforcement fibres. The latter reduces the stress concentration at the thin section. The belt sub-laminate geometric and meshing arrangement considered here is the one already presented in Ref. [14]. The high fidelity model comprised also the expected change in fibre volume fractions due to the local thickness variation.

Figure 9. Refined belt shape FE model

In the high fidelity model, a thermal expansion step was also performed prior to the mechanical analysis, in order to account for the effects of the residual stresses induced by the post-cure cooling. The estimated bending moment to grow the crack for the high fidelity model was 28.6kN, which is 16% higher than the actual value obtained during the experiments. Moreover the propagation occurred only at the bottom thick section interface. The location of the delamination growth has therefore proven to be highly dependent on the fine details of the ply-drop geometric arrangement, which also show a high degree of variability from specimen to specimen. This suggests that an idealized ply-drop configuration should be

considered in the FE models, since this yields conservative results.

An overall summary of the experimental and FE results is presented in tab. 2.

	Onset load (kN)	Onset location	Failure load (kN)
Experimental	23.8 (C.V. 4.8%)	Thin section	46.2 (C.V. 3.4%)
FE idealised	20.7	Thin section	44.6
FE High fidelity	28.6	Thick section	50

Table 2. Results summary

4. Conclusions

Quasi-isotropic asymmetrically tapered laminates were loaded in tension to investigate the effect of ply drop-offs on the axial strength, particularly in terms of the onset and growth of delaminations. Strain gauges and high speed video recordings were used to identify and monitor the onset and propagation of delaminations from the ply drop-off regions.

High speed camera images clearly identified delaminations being initiated at the thin section for the specimen arrangement considered here. This consistently occurred for a set of inter ply drop-off distances ranging from 5 mm to 20 mm. No significant effect of the inter-drop distance was observed on the tapered laminate strength.

The idealized VCCT-based FE model has accurately predicted the location of the crack initiation. The FE gave an onset load 13% lower than the one observed during testing for the thin section delamination. The final failure load predicted by the FE was only 5% smaller than the one observed in the tests.

The results from image-based FE models also suggest that the thickness profile of the belt sub-laminate, the local fibre orientation and the reinforcement volume fraction all play a major role in determining where and at which load the delamination onset occurs. This in turns has a significant impact on the laminate strength. Since all these parameters are affected by a large degree of uncertainty, idealized ply drop-off models provide a robust tool for assessing the strength of tapered laminates.

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